

Spoken Songs: Algorithms of Composition and Improvisation. Project Data

Version 1

Description

The project focuses on 'spoken songs', the oldest layer of Latvian traditional vocal music, characterized by narrow-range melodies shaped by the text delivery and improvisation. By combining algorithmic and qualitative methods, the project aims to understand principles of composition and improvisation in the performance tradition of 'spoken songs' and the Latvian folk songs in general.

The project data will contain: an encoded corpus of spoken song melodies, a selected encoded corpus of folk song text strings, a database of sources of melodic variation, three corpora of regional repertoires, and an annotated bibliography.

The project "Spoken Songs: Algorithms of Composition and Improvisation" is implemented in the framework of the Fundamental and Applied Research Programme (project No. lzp-2025/1-0252).

Project page: <https://lulfmi.lv/en/research/projects/spoken-songs-algorithms-of-composition-and-improvisation>

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Spoken Songs: Algorithms of
Composition and
Improvisation. Project Data

Researchers

Ieva Weaver (0000-0003-3363-3552), Ginta Perle-Sile (0000-0002-4305-3343), Martin Boiko (0009-0004-1726-2696), Kārlis Freivalds (0000-0003-2684-559X), Linda Luīze Barbare (0009-0001-7924-5136), Arta Krūze (0009-0004-4424-5357), Davis Engelis (0009-0007-6440-8186)

Organizations

Institute of Literature, Folklore and Art of the University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Spoken Songs: Algorithms of Composition and Improvisation. Project Data](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#) | [LCS](#)

Grants: [Spoken Songs: Algorithms of Composition and Improvisation. Project Data](#)

Project:

3. License

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Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

A selective corpus of Latvian folk song texts

A selective corpus of 10,000 folk song texts will be created. The source will be an unpublished folk song catalogue made for the academic edition "Latvian Folk Songs" in 1970–2023. This is the most complete catalogue, almost unused in former studies, as it was completed only recently.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The data will be used for algorithmic analysis for pattern recognition and studying the composition and improvisation techniques.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Machine-readable text
- Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- HTML

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

Archives of Latvian Folklore

<https://humma.lv/en>

id: null, Type: other

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Folklore researchers, digital humanists, literary scholars

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

Historical international folklore archiving guidelines

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Access will be provided for registered users on request.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Internet connection, internet browser

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Data will be available for download in .csv, .xls.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

Taxonomy used in Latvian folk song classification

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-06-30

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Data are selected, prepared and double-checked by experts in the field of folklore studies, Latvian folklore, and archiving.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Funded by the project "Spoken Songs: Algorithms of Composition and Improvisation", Fundamental and Applied Research Program, No. lzp-2025/1-0252.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

- Ginta Perle-Sīle (0000-0002-4305-3343)
- Ieva Weaver (0000-0003-3363-3552)
- Linda Luīze Barbare (0009-0001-7924-5136)
- Arta Krūze (0009-0004-4424-5357)

Ginta Pērle-Sīle, Arta Krūze, Linda Barbare - content selection, preparation of the dataset.

Ieva Weaver - project managing, supervision.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

The maintenance will be funded from the budget of the Institute of Literature, Folklore and Art of the University of Latvia.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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